

Reproducibility of the paper: Expert Finding in Legal Community Question Answering

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The aim of this report is to assess the reproducibility of the results in the paper Expert finding in legal community question answering from Askari et al. We were unable to reproduce the paper, and we are going to explain more in detail later in the next sections.

1 INTRODUCTION

The paper Expert Finding in Legal Community Question Answering from Askari et al., proposes methods for generating query-dependent textual profiles for lawyers covering several aspects including sentiment, comments, and recency. Since this topic has not been studied by other papers, the authors tried a new method on how to solve this problem. They define and evaluate legal expert finding methods on legal CQA data. Their contribution cited in their papers are as follows:

- 1) Defining the task of lawyer finding and release a test collection for the task
- 2) Evaluation of the applicability of existing expert finding methods for lawyer finding, both probabilistic and BERT-based;
- 3) Creation of query-dependent profiles of lawyers representing different aspects.

We are going to explain their work more in depth in the next section.

2 OVERVIEW

The authors of the paper used 2 different baselines to compare their method in finding the legal expert for a domain, given the query. The first baselines were two probabilistic language modelling, candidate-based modelling and document-based modelling. We are not going to explain in depth these models, but just some definition to create an idea about their work. In the **Candidate-based model**, they created a textual representation of a lawyer's knowledge based on the answers written by them. In the **Document-based model**, the document-centric model builds a bridge between a query and lawyers by considering documents in the collection as link. The formulas are well defined in the paper. The Candidate-based model is denoted as model 2, and the Document-based model is denoted as model 1.

The second baseline is the Vanilla BERT model. This model is a pre-trained BERT model (BERT-Base, Uncased) with a linear combination layer stacked atop the classifier [CLS] token that is fine-tuned on the paper's chosen dataset in a pairwise cross-entropy loss setting using the Adam optimizer.

Their proposed approach is combination of the models used as baselines. For every given query and a collection of answers by different lawyers, they retrieve a ranked list of answers from the model 1. Then, they create four different profiles for the lawyers who have at least one answer, from the ranked list found by the model 1, given the query. Each profile consists of text, and that text is sampled to represent different aspects of a lawyer's answers. The aspects are comments, sentiment-positive, sentiment-negative, and recency.

The Vanilla-BERT model is fine-tuned on each profile. The scores are then aggregated from the four profile BERT models and BERT-Document-based using a linear combination of the five model's scores. The weights of the aggregated score, are optimized using grid search in the range [1,100].

3 REPRODUCTION

3.1 Data Loading

Unfortunately, the data was not provided by the authors. From their repository in github [2], it was provided a file with links in json format from the website, Avvo forum, they got the data. Since we did not have the data they worked on, we tried to scrape the data from the links they provided, with the help of Selenium package.

Another problem we faced was the data protection from the website, so we could not download all the information needed to replicate the approach as mentioned by the paper. For example, a problem would be missing category tag, which gives important information about the lawyers. This essential part of the data would be needed to appropriately classify the expert in this case and to filter the lawyers in the manner previously described. For this reason, the data would not be the same as the authors used, to evaluate the models in the paper [1].

3.2 Reconstructing model 1 and model 2

The model 1 and 2, the document-based model and candidate-based model, are the probabilistic language models used in this paper. We faced a lot of difficulties replicating their work.

Firstly, the code given would not work for different reasons. Elasticsearch would be a problem and after a lot of different changes would work but not in the desired manner.

Secondly, the data would not be very compatible with the code, and after reverse engineering would work, but still with no result. The main issue for both models seems to be Elasticsearch with other minor problems, which would make working with the given codes very frustrating. For more see details in [2].

3.3 Reconstructing Vanilla-BERT

This model would be fine-tuned by the dataset they scrapped from the forum. After initial ranking with model 2, they would fine-tune Vanilla BERT to estimate the relevance between query and answer terms as mentioned. They would relate their work from [3]. Without reconstructing the model 2, we could not reproduce the results from Vanilla-BERT model. But also, if we could the problem would not end there. Since the code for Vanilla-BERT model was referred from another work, this would make our work more difficult, see [4]. Not just the Vanilla-BERT model referred from another paper was not working, but also was pretrained with another dataset. Another problem we faced from the code given, was the use of another package called “pytrec_eval”, which would be installed via git, since the code is available in GitHub [5]. Unfortunately, it would not get installed.

3.4 Reconstructing the proposed method

Since their approach is a combination of the models above, we were not able to reconstruct their work.

Firstly, the problem would be the absence of the ranked list from model 1, given a query. For each query, they would create four profiles for the lawyers, who have at least one answer from the list found from model 1. The profiles would be comments, sentiment-positive, sentiment-negative, and recency. They would fine-tune Vanilla-BERT model for each profile and fine-tune the BERT model with the document-based model. The score would be an aggregate score from the five models.

4 RESULTS

In the paper the approach proposed seems to outperform the baseline models.

The metrics used are MAP (Mean Average Precision), MRR (Mean reciprocal rank) and P@n (which is Precision@1,2 and 5).

Model	MAP	MRR	P@1	P@2	P@5
Model 1 (Candidate-based) LM	22.8%	40.9%	23.9%	19.7%	13.2%
Model 1 (Candidate-based) BM25	3.7%	7.0%	2.9%	1.4%	2.6%
Model 2 (Document-based) LM	19.4%	21.9%	13.5%	12.7%	7.8%
Model 2 (Document-based) BM25	21.0%	36.6%	22.5%	18.3%	11.5%
Vanilla BERT Document-based (VBD)	37.3%*	70.7%*	60.5%*	55.6%*	25.9%*
VBD + Profiles (weighted)	39.3%*•	73.2%	64.9%*•	57.1%	27.7%*•

Figure 1: The results from the [1]. VBD + Profiles is the proposed model

We could not replicate the work from the [1], due to aforementioned reasons. We were not able to do any statistical test, or any other interpretation.

5. PROBLEMS

A. Code/Setup Difficulties	YES	NO
Code not provided		X
Code partially not provided		X
Faulty code provided	X	
Info. about software version missing	X	
Specific hardware setup necessary	X	
B. Data		
Data not provided	X	
Data partially not provided		X
Metadata not provided		X
C. Process		
Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed		X
Experimental setup not described		X
Experiment workflow incomplete		X
Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	X	
Results differ significantly	X	

Our work is in Github: <https://github.com/OzgeOzkaya/TUWien-Experiment-Design/tree/main>

REFERENCES

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- [4] <https://github.com/Georgetown-IR-Lab/cedr>
- [5] https://github.com/cvangysel/pytrec_eval